

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: VODOUNOU****FIRST NAME: KAFUI****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: SIX (6)****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 5%

The author used the following software: MSWord Office Standard 2019 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-410D RP6

1. Which initiative should a student take to start writing their thesis?

Starting to write the thesis with a question that other researchers would want to explore.

Asking key questions, finding answers that show evidenced base, finding reliable data, suggesting an argument supporting the arguments in the paper and ensuring that all findings presented are evidenced-based information.¹

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23.

- Having an interest, a focused topic and a plan before writing the thesis.
- Making a list of possible topics, discussing the issue with an academic instructor and finding rich resources at the library in the field of interest.

2. According to Turabian's Manual for Writers, what planning structure should a thesis follow?

- An introduction, method and materials, results, discussion, conclusion and bibliography
- A storyboard which plans and guides the research work over several pages, with lots of space for adding data and ideas. The storyboard makes the reading flow.²**
- The structure of a thesis is represented in minor sections below the major ones to create a picture of the project design
- The presentation of arguments is to organise the thesis for a better understanding of a first drafted version.

3. Which initial step should a student take when approaching a research topic?

² Ibid., 32.

- The student should have a list of essential questions reflecting on the different topics of interest and have a literature review
- The student should choose a topic that they are passionate about but not too personal, an environment where they can collect the data in a given period.
- The student should confidently choose a topic, collect all relevant information, and discuss it with the academic instructor.
- The student should confidently choose a topic according to their interest because it is a subject of enquiry around a particular research problem that their thesis will address.³**

4. In which section of the thesis can the reader understand how the proposed project would conduct and assess the quality of the approach used by the writer?

- The research design section
- The argument section
- The discussion section

³ Linda D. Blomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications Ltd, 2008), 6.

The methodology section.⁴

5. Which qualitative research approach refers to the belief that some laws or theories govern the world and these can be tested and verified?

Social Constructivism

Critical Theory

Pragmatic

Post-positivism.⁵

6. As recommended by Professor Adu, which of the following are the most common philosophical paradigms used:

Axiology and epistemology.

Ontology and Axiology.

Ontology and epistemology.⁶

Ethnography and Axiology.

⁴ Blomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 81.

⁵ Ibid., 8.

⁶ Philip Adu, "Conducting Qualitative Research: Writing the Methodology Chapter" (The Chicago School of Professional Psychology, Chicago, February 03 2016).

7. In Turabian's Manual for Writers, which elements assemble to build research arguments?

- Claim and evidence
- Claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgement and response and warrant.**⁷
- Reason, evidence, acknowledgement and response and warrant
- Evidence

8. When most of their quantitative evidence focuses on trends, what is the recommendation to the student?

- The student should present the data graphically
- The student can design tables, bar charts and line graphs
- The student should present the data using bar charts
- The student should present the data using a line graph.**⁸

9. According to *The WHO Style Guide*, how would a student reproduce or adapt a figure, table, photograph or other

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations*, 58.

⁸ Ibid., 86.

illustration from material already published by another publisher?

- The student should reproduce the table and reference under the figure according to the choice of referencing style.
- The student must obtain permission from the copyright holder.⁹**
- The student should adapt with a photograph and indicate the origin of the source in the appendix section.
- The student must reference any materials used in their thesis in the bibliography and appendices section.

10. Based on *The WHO Style Guide*, how would a student write the name of a person working in an international institution in their thesis?

- Oxfam Director-General Manager Paul Smith.¹⁰**
- Paul Smith, General Director, Oxfam
- Paul Smith, Oxfam (General-Director)
- Oxfam, Paul Smith (General Director)

⁹ World Health Organization (WHO), *WHO Style Guide* (World Health Organization Press, 2013), 49.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*,17.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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